

Microwave induced synthesis of 3-substituted 1,2-benzisoxazole derivatives

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Abstract : A rapid, cost-effective and eco-friendly synthesis of 3-substituted 1,2-benzisoxazoles from *o*-hydroxy ketoximes in solvent free conditions using solid support under microwave irradiation has been achieved.

Keywords : 1,2-Benzisoxazoles, microwave, silica gel, sodium carbonate oxime.

Introduction

The base catalyzed synthesis of 1,2-benzisoxazoles¹⁻³ is one of the most elegant methods which involves the attack of phenoxide ion on the nitrogen of oxime or its derivatives to give 1,2-benzisoxazoles. These compounds can also be synthesized by converting phenolic hydroxyl group of *o*-hydroxy ketoxime into a better leaving group and the resulting derivatives in base give 1,2-benzisoxazoles⁴. These reactions were carried in organic solvents which are more expensive, having prolonged reaction times and tedious work-up procedures. Thus a milder, more selective and inexpensive reaction is still in demand.

The use of microwave irradiation for rapid organic synthesis has found widespread applications due to substantial reduction in reaction time^{5, 6}, better yield, easier work up and solvent free reaction conditions. Keeping these points in mind, we undertook the synthesis of the title compounds from *o*-hydroxy ketoxime by using silica and sodium carbonate as solid support under microwave irradiation.

Results and discussion

Cyclization of various substituted *o*-hydroxy ketoximes (**1a-l**) with a mixture of silica gel (60–120 mesh) and sodium carbonate under microwave irradiation afforded 3-substituted 1,2-benzisoxazoles (**2a-l**, Scheme 1). The reaction was completed within 3–4 min at 100% power at 2450 MHz to obtain 1,2-benzisoxazoles in excellent yields. Solid supports are poor thermal conductors but strong microwave adsorbents⁷. Thus in order to maximize microwave effect, solid support silica gel was essential. When a mixture of *o*-hydroxy ketoximes and sodium carbonate was irradiated with microwave radiation at 100% power without silica gel 1,2-benzisoxazoles (**2a-l**) were obtained in very poor yield. Reaction is specific for ketoximes but aldoximes responded in poor yield.

The IR spectrum of all the products showed bands at 1620–1650 cm⁻¹ (C=N) and is consistent with the absence of OH stretching vibration (3360 cm⁻¹). Similarly, the absence of signal in the ¹H NMR spectrum for OH proton supports the structure. These compounds gave negative ferric chloride test and products are insoluble in dilute sodium hydroxide. The m.p., mixed m.p., TLC and superimposable IR were found to be identical with authentic samples^{2,4}.

Based on the results it was concluded that the reaction products are 3-substituted 1,2-benzisoxazoles. In summary, the present procedure for synthesis of title compounds provides an easy, mild, efficient, versatile and general methodology for the preparation of 3-substituted 1,2-benzisoxazole derivatives.

Scheme 1

Note

Physical and ¹ H NMR spectral data of compounds 2a-l										
Compd.	R'	R				M.p. (°C)		Time (min)	Yields (%)	¹ H NMR data (δ)
		4	5	6	7	Observed	Reported			
2a	CH ₃	H	Cl	CH ₃	H	115	116 ²	3	94	2.3 (3H, s, 3-CH ₃), 2.4 (3H, s, 6-CH ₃), 7.15 (1H, s, Ar-H), 7.5 (1H, s, Ar-H)
2b	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	H	H	Liquid	Liquid ⁴	3	95	2.4 (3H, s, 3-CH ₃), 2.5 (3H, s, 5-CH ₃), 7.3-7.6 (3H, m, Ar-H)
2c	CH ₃	H	H	CH ₃	H	Liquid	Liquid ²	3	90	2.3 (3H, s, 3-CH ₃), 2.45 (3H, s, 6-CH ₃), 7.3-7.5 (3H, m, Ar-H)
2d	CH ₃	H	Cl	H	H	55	54 ⁴	3	85	2.3 (3H, s, 3-CH ₃), 7.0-7.6 (3H, m, Ar-H)
2e	CH ₃	H	Br	H	H	43	43 ²	3	80	2.3 (3H, s, 3-CH ₃), 7.0 (1H, s, Ar-H), 7.5-7.68 (2H, m, Ar-H)
2f	CH ₃	H	H	H	H	Liquid	Liquid ²	3	90	2.35 (3H, s, 3-CH ₃), 7.2 (4H, s, Ar-H)
2g	C ₆ H ₅	H	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	83	82 ²	4	90	2.5 (6H, s, 5-CH ₃ and 7-CH ₃), 7.2 (7H, s, Ar-H)
2h	C ₆ H ₅	H	Cl	CH ₃	H	119	118 ⁴	4	87	2.5 (3H, s, 6-CH ₃), 7.2-7.55 (7H, m, Ar-H)
2i	C ₆ H ₅	H	Cl	H	Cl	91	91 ⁴	4	92	7.2-8.1 (7H, m, Ar-H)
2j	C ₆ H ₅	H	Cl	H	H	89	89 ²	4	90	7.0-7.8 (8H, m, Ar-H)
2k	C ₂ H ₅	H	CH ₃	H	H	Liquid	Liquid ²	3.5	95	2.3 (3H, s, 5-CH ₃), 2.4 (3H, t, 3-CH ₃), 3.8 (2H, q, CH ₂), 7.1 (1H, s, Ar-H), 7.2-7.3 (2H, m, Ar-H)
2f	C ₂ H ₅	H	Cl	H	Cl	64	64 ²	3.5	93	2.35 (3H, t, 3-CH ₃), 3.9 (2H, q, CH ₂), 7.4 (1H, s, Ar-H), 7.55 (1H, s, Ar-H)

Experimental

Melting points were recorded on sulphuric acid bath and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer using KBr pellet. ¹H NMR was recorded on various spectrophotometers in CDCl₃ at 300 MHz by using TMS as internal standard.

Microwave reactions were carried out using LG555f multipower microwave oven operating at 2450 MHz frequency. Purity of compounds was checked by TLC on silica gel-G coated Al plates (Merck). Required substituted *o*-hydroxy ketoximes were prepared by the procedure reported in literature².

General procedure for cyclization of oxime to 3-substituted 1,2-benzisoxazole (2a-l) :

0.01 mmol of *o*-hydroxy ketoxime was dissolved in dichloromethane (10 ml). In another beaker silica gel (10 g) of 60-120 mesh was treated with 0.02 mmol of sodium carbonate solution, stirred and dried. This dried mixture was transferred to *o*-hydroxy ketoxime solution and the solvent was evaporated in vacuum. Resulting mix-

ture was moistened with water (8-10 drops), stirred well; water was essential to increase the yield of reaction. Then reaction mixture was kept inside a microwave oven and irradiated for about 3-4 min with intermittent cooling at every half minute interval. The cooling was necessary to avoid the loss of product by evaporation. The reaction mixture was cooled and the product was extracted by dichloromethane (5 × 10 ml) filtered and the solvent was evaporated in vacuum. Residue was treated with 5% NaOH for 30 min, in order to remove the unreacted oxime. Obtained 1,2-benzisoxazole (2a-l) was filtered, washed with water and crystallized from ethanol.

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